

METAL FRAMED TOP TILE CENTER TABLE WITH ROUND BAR STAND

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at fabricating metal framed top tile center table which was conducted ta Benguet State University- Bokod Campus from January to May 2024. Descriptive pre-experimental research design was used in the study. In the pre-experimental aspect , a metal framed top tile center table was fabricated and subjected to evaluation for data collection on suggestions for improvement. Then another metal framed top tile center table was fabricated and subjected to evaluation for data collection on acceptability of design, durability, sustainability, selling price, benefits, drawbacks and suggestions for improvement. It was found out in this study that using lapped joint in connecting 2” under support bars to the metal frame might have enhanced the loading capacity of the granite tile and the use of 60 degree angle on the base of the legs might increased the loading capacity of the metal legs. It was was found out that the design of the 67cm by 67 cm by 18” metal framed top tile center table was observed as outstanding while excellent in terms of durability and sustainability. Further, the 40% mark up price based on production cost was strongly accepted. However, installation of threaded legs was suggested by 55% of the participants for adjustments on uneven surfaces. It was concluded in the study that the metal framed top tile center table can be commercialized upon registration to the intellectual property rights office of BSU and integration to civil technology courses.

Keywords: *center table, Metal framed, Top tile, Lapped joint, tensile strength, loading capacity, under support bars*

INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains the background and significance of the study and relevant information, objectives of the study, conceptual framework, statement of the problem and necessary literature for the study. This leads the reader from a general subject related to a particular field of study.

Background of the study

A United Nations global survey conducted in 2017 aimed at identifying emerging future issues identified sustainable economic development as question prevails. The report noted: "Never before has world public opinion been as unified on a single goal as it is today "achieve sustainable development". The current trend of consuming the earth's resources is unsustainable and creates major environmental problems. Climate change, resource depletion, biodiversity loss, and air. The current use of Earth's limited resources cannot be sustained. There is a must to aim for sustainable developments to "meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Brundtland, 2017). These perspectives were supported with the idea that the use of rotary veneer bentwood is highly encouraged over solid wood in support to Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12 particularly the goal on responsible production (Hartanto, 2024). However this idea still involve the use of forests product that may still cause deforestation.

Rapid deforestation is one of the most pressing problems that confront various countries. The loss of forests can lead to erosion, disrupted water cycles, etc. Efforts to address deforestation typically involve a combination of policies, regulations, and sustainable practices. These may include stricter logging regulations, supporting responsible but sustainable furniture production practices, and raising awareness about the importance of preserving forests(Malin et al. 2012). Although it was clearly stated in the 1987 Philippine Constitution Article II, Section 16 that the State shall protect and advance the right of the people to a balanced and healthful ecology in accord with the rhythm and harmony of nature. This is also in line with the World SDG 13 initiative which aims to combat climate change and states that forests are important part of the global carbon cycle (Carlota, 2015).

Grounded by the above premises, innovation in furniture fabrication is an urgent need to conserve forests products but still sustain furniture industry. These concepts were supported with the findings of a study that utilization of sustainable non forests materials for furniture positioned well the product in the market (Bumgardner, 2020) but this study failed to identify specific non forests sustainable materials for center table.

Research Objectives

Generally, the study aimed to investigate how the combination of a metal structure with a top tile in a center table can offer an interesting alternative to traditional designs, including dual goals about aesthetics and sustainable interventions that will

minimize the use of wood. Integrating these materials can create a center table that is not only visually appealing but also stands the test of time in terms of sturdiness and longevity.

Ultimately, the general aim of the study is to develop a metal framed top tile center table. It specifically aimed to:

1. To fabricate metal framed top tile center table with 60 degrees leg base, lapped under support frame and screwed mounted legs.
2. Assess the metal framed tile top center table in terms of;
 - a. Design
 - b. Durability
 - c. Sustainability
3. To determine the acceptability of the selling price based on production cost
4. To determine the main benefits of metal framed tile top center table.
5. To characterize the drawbacks and suggestions for the improvement of metal framed top tile center table.

Significance of the study

Researching innovation on eco-friendly and sustainable furniture is crucial for a number of reasons. Firstly, it helps reduce the environmental impact of furniture production and consumption. By using sustainable materials and production methods, furniture manufacturers can minimize their carbon footprint and waste. Secondly, eco-friendly furniture is healthier for people and the environment. Thirdly, sustainable furniture is often more durable and long-lasting than traditional furniture, which can save consumers money in the long run (Bumgardner et al. 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Overall, researching eco-friendly and sustainable furniture innovation is essential for reducing environmental impact and creating innovative and competitive furniture designs. Eco-friendly but sustainable furniture practices include using non forests products support sustainable environment (R. A. Houghton et al. 2019). Further, eco-friendly connotes applying the principle of high durability but lesser environmental impact (Das et al. 2021).

Research Design

Descriptive pre-experimental research design was used in this study. The pre-experimental part was the fabrication of center table

Place and time of the study

The study was conducted at Bokod, Benguet, Philippines. Specifically at Benguet State University-Bokod Campus. It was started in January 2024 and ended on July 2024. The researcher employed several laboratory methodologies and evaluation. BSU-Bokod Campus was chosen as the locale of the study because industrial arts laboratory facilities are accessible to the researcher. Secondly, there were sufficient number of college

students with industrial arts major. Lastly, BSU-Bokod is just 50 meters away from Ambangeg National High School with faculty major in industrial arts who were considered as respondents.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study composed of forty (40) individuals. Twelve (12) came from the TVL teachers of Ambangeg NHS and Eight (8) industrial arts instructors of BSU-Bokod Campus while twenty (20) came from the industrial arts (BTLED & BTVTED) students of BSU-Bokod Campus.

Purposive sampling was used in identifying the participants of this study. Volunteer participants were identified and categorized based on occupational status.

Data Collection Instrument

A Four (4) likert scale survey questionnaire (Kaputa et al. 2019) was used which comprised of 4 parts. (Please refer to appendix B)

Part I contained the questions for participant's category and major field while part II of the instrument comprised the three components of table for evaluation which were further simplified into elementary components respectively. The first component was design. This was simplified into three elementary sub components which are customization, aesthetic appeal and functionality Second was durability which was broken down into load capacity, material quality and construction quality.

Lastly was sustainability which was itemized into life cycle analysis, material sourcing and manufacturing processes.

Part III composed of questions pertaining to production cost, selling cost, benefits and drawbacks of the top tile center table.

Part IV contained the open-ended question on the suggestion or recommendations for the improvement of the top tile center table.

Data Collection Procedures

A letter of request to conduct was prepared and worked for its approval. After which, the evaluation of the metal framed top tile center table with 67 cm x 67 cm by 16" was conducted using the adapted 4 point likert acceptability survey questionnaire Based on the evaluation another table with dimension of 67 cm x 67 cm by 18" was fabricated then subjected to acceptability test. using the same survey questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This part of the study presents the metal framed top tile center tables as output of the pre-experimental and the outcome of the evaluation. Results are discussed and verified to related studies. Implications of data were also identified.

Responses from the survey questionnaire were gathered, recorded, tallied, organized and summarized for calculation.

Fabrication of metal framed top tile center table with 60 degrees leg base, lapped tile support frame and screwed mounted legs

A metal framed top tile center table was fabricated using granite tile with dimensions of 67 cm by 67cm. Granite tile was found to be the hardest tile (P. Torres et al. 2017) based on literature review. Based on the calculated loading capacity of 67 cm by 67 cm granite tile which is 1020-3630 psi, this denotes that one 67 cm by 67 cm granite tile has loading capacity of 71.7 kgs-255.21kgs. With the 370-440 MPa tensile strength of each of four flat metal bars used as under support to the granite tile, this connotes high resistance of the flat bars to stress when greater pressure is exerted to the top tile base. Having frame of 2" square bars with tensile strength of 58,000 psi, it surfaced that the frame has high resistant to pressure (Pavlina et al. 2008).

The calculations of tensile strength of metals used and the loading capacity of the granite top tile showed that the fabricated center table is resistant to pressure. This findings is supported by the theory that output strength and flexural strength have linear correlation with hardness (Pavlina, 2008).

The special features of the fabricated metal framed top tile table comprised the use of 60 degrees angle on the base of its legs to enhance the loading capacity of the legs. 60 degree angle was established in between the folded 1/2" round bar which provided increase of stress resistance on the legs. This was based on the theory that when angle decreases, the stress on each leg increases (Onur, 2018).

Further, lapped joint seemingly prevented easy detachment of under support bars. This assumption is supported with the concepts that lapped joint have tensile strength of 110MPa. This might mean that a single lap joint has the capacity to load 112.69 kilos (MPa to kg/conversion table) when welding processes are applied ((Danielewski et al. 2020).

In addition, permanent attachment of granite tile on the frame may prevent possible breakage for it is assumed that detachable top tile is prone to breakage.

Assessment of the metal framed tile top center table in terms of a) Design, b) Durability and c) Sustainability

Based on the survey conducted, the following are the components of design

Table 5. Distribution of Responses on the Design

Components of Design	Mean	Interpretation
Customization	3.20	The design is outstanding
Aesthetic appeal	3.45	The design is outstanding
Functionality	3.45	The design is outstanding

Legend: 1:00-1.49-poor, 1.50-2.49-good,2.50-3.49-very good, 3.50-4.49-excellent

Based on the calculated mean of 3.45, the 67 cm by 67 cm by 18” metal framed top tile center table was evaluated as outstanding in terms of design specifically on aspects of aesthetic appeal, and functionality. Although, customization has lowest mean of 3.2, this component was affirmed outstanding. These findings denote that aesthetic appeal and functionality are seen as essential factors of design over customization of design. These findings were backed up by the findings of the previous study asserting that humans tend to appreciate furniture by integrating aesthetic appeal with functionality.

Table 6 Distribution of Responses on the Durability

Components of Durability	Mean	Interpretation
Load capacity	3.65	There is observable excellence in durability
Material quality	3.70	There is observable excellence in durability
Construction quality	3.70	There is observable excellence in durability

N=40

Legend: 1:00-1.49-poor, 1.50-2.49-good,2.50-3.49-very good, 3.50-4.49-excellent

In terms of durability, the metal framed top tile center table was assessed as excellent in terms of material and construction quality with the highest mean of 3.7. Load capacity has the lowest mean of 3.65. These might imply that there was observable excellence in terms of construction quality, material quality over load capacity. Similar findings were revealed from the study of Khojaste (2020) which asserted that the primary criteria for buying furniture is product quality and guaranteed features. Furthermore, it assumed that consumers buying decisions are influenced by the visual/appearance and economical features of the furniture. These findings were substantiated with the calculated tensile strength of metals and loading capacity of the granite tile used (Pavlina et al. 2008). Further, it was backed up with the assumption that lapped joint may enhance the loading capacity of the under support bars to approximately 112.69 (Danielewski et al. 2020).

Table 7 Distribution of Responses on the Sustainability

Components of Sustainability	Mean	Interpretation
Life Cycle Analysis	3.60	There is observable excellence in sustainability.
Material Sourcing	3.78	There is observable excellence in sustainability.
Manufacturing Process	3.63	There is observable excellence in sustainability.
N=40		

Legend: 1:00-1.49-poor, 1.50-2.49-good,2.50-3.49-very good, 3.50-4.49-excellent

Moreover, the evaluation of the center table in terms of the components of sustainability surfaced that material sourcing has the highest mean of 3.78 while life cycle analysis has the lowest mean of 3.6. These findings might mean that there was observable excellence in material sourcing over life cycle analysis. Availability of materials may have associated with sustainability of production (Iritani et al. 2015).

To determine the acceptability of the selling cost based on production cost

The calculated production cost was 2,525 inclusive of materials and labor costs. Its calculated selling costs was 3,535. The selling prices was determined by computing 40% of the production costs as the mark up price (Philippine -Pricing, 2019). Allowable mark up price lift from Philippine-Pricing guideline for luxury items is 20-30% with additional 10% value added tax.

Table 8 Agreement on the Production Cost and Selling Price

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation
Selling cost (3535)	3.75	There was strong agreement on the selling cost
N=40		

Legend: 1:00-1.49 disagree, 1.50-2.49-agree ,2.50-3.49-moderately agree, 3.50-4.49-strongly agree

There was strong agreement on the selling cost based on the production cost. These findings may mean that there was strong agreement on the 40% mark up price. Previous literature theorizes and shows that price is an important marketplace cue and that consumers interpret high prices as a signal of high sustainable product quality (Doorn, 2021).

To determine the main benefits of metal framed tile top center table.

Table 9. Benefits from the Innovated Center Table

Benefits	Mean	Interpretation
It has a sleek design that matches my style	3.73	There was strong agreement on the sleek design

It has a durable surface that resists scratches and stains	3.75	There was strong agreement on the durability of surface
It saves space and allows easy set up and storage	3.78	There was strong agreement on the ability of the center table to save space, easy set up and easy to store

N=40

Legend: 1:00-1.49 disagree, 1.50-2.49-agree ,2.50-3.49-moderately agree, 3.50-4.49 strongly agree

As to benefits gained from the metal framed top tile center table, saving spaces and easy to set up and store were the main benefits identified with mean of 3.78 over sleek design with mean of 3.73. These might imply that the center table save space, easy to store and easy to set up which may due to its size. These findings was supported with the concept that small furniture provide space on narrow spaces and occupy small spaces (Asraf, 2019).

To characterize the drawbacks and suggestions for the improvement of metal framed top tile center table.

Table 10. Draw backs of Innovative center Table

Drawbacks of innovative table	Mean	Interpretation
It is too heavy or bulky to move around	1.38	There was disagreement that the center table is too heavy or bulky to move around
It is too small or large for my needs	1.15	There was disagreement that the center table is small or too large for their needs
It is not stable, not comfortable or sturdy enough	1.13	There was disagreement that the center table is not stable, comfortable or sturdy

N=40

Legend 1.0-1.49 disagree, 1.50-2.49 agree, 2.50-3.49 moderately agree, 3.50-4.49 strongly agree

There was disagreement that the innovated center table was too heavy or bulky to move around with a mean of 1.38. Further, there was also disagreement that the center table was too small or large for their needs with mean of 1.15. Likewise there was disagreement that the table was not stable or comfortable or sturdy with mean of 1.13. These findings might imply that there was no identified drawbacks of the metal framed top tile center table.

Suggestions were coded, grouped and organized into theme which are presented below.

Table 11. Suggestions for Improvement

Theme	Respondents' #	Suggestions for improvement
Install adjustable legs for uneven surfaces	# 40	"Mayat no guaray threaded ja poste to"
	#36	"make the legs adjustable"
	#35	"adjustable komay sede to say angken may taken shohtog"
	#39	"aknim kare ni threaded ja sede to"
	#27	"para patag lang ta awan adjustment saka na"
	#25	"mayat sa met no ada thread saka na"
	#21	"ekam thread na ta uray awitin karayan no picnic"
	#19	"put adjustment device on legs para okay sa bato bato"
	#17	"Install threaded post for adjusting for uneven surfaces"
	#16	"quality nem ampet patad kausalan to"
	#15	"ampet panpatag ngoy panpowesto an to"
	#12	"mabadin emon guay adjust an tod ma sede to"
	#11	"pag lagyan kaya ng parte para adjustable ang leegs niya"
	#9	"Quality but not suited for uneven surfaces"
	#8	"di pwede sa kabundukan"
#7	"aknim kare ni device ja ama posipos sede to say angken eg nay level eh dota makahtan pay sede to"	
#6	"paano kayang makatayo sa elevated location"	
#5	"ampet ashekdanan e ahtanan to, aknim kare kay adjust an ni sede to"	
#4	"sano ngata no guay remedjoan ni sede to say angken shema atenshel ket on dayat"	
#3	"Mayat nem singa poweg eya sede to ja angken pan enoyad nem kasapulan"	
#2	"et estay kosto nem guay thread nita, sede to say may ojad no kailangan weno patekey"	
#1	"what if you make the legs adjustable"	

Based on the coded data, it appeared that the suggestions maybe group into theme which is installation of threaded posts to suit the demand of elevated spaces or stony surfaces like for example the suggestion of res. # 4 “sano ngata no guay remedjoan ni sede to say angken shema atenshel ket on dayat” which has the same point of res #2, “ et estay kosto nem guay thread nita sede to say may ojad no kailangan weno patekey. These findings were backed up by the concept that millennial consumers prefer furniture with removable and adjustable component (Taylor, 2020)

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were lifted:

1. Use of lapped joint and 2” flat bar as under support of granite tile can enhance the tensile strength of granite support bars and 60 degree angle on the base of the legs can improve the loading capacity of 67 cm by 67 cm by 18” metal framed top tile center table.
2. The design was observed as outstanding while the durability and sustainability were excellent.
3. There was strong agreement on the 40% mark up price based on production cost.
4. Space saving and convenience in storing and setting up were the identified benefits.
5. There were no drawbacks identified but installation of threaded posts was suggested to meet the demands of uneven surfaces

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn based on findings.

1. The use of lapped joint is recommended in the joining of under support bars and 60 degrees angle is recommended to be used at the base of the center table legs to increase loading capacity.
2. Since the metal framed top tile center table was observed as outstanding on design and excellent on durability and sustainability, it is recommended that the product would be commercialized after registration to intellectual property rights office of Benguet State University and be integrated in the Civil Technology course.
3. Considering that 40% mark up price has strong agreement, it is recommended that when commercialize the ceiling mark up price may not exceed 40% base on the allowable percentage of mark up price in the Philippines (RA 6361)

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